

Phytochemical Screening and Evaluation of Antioxidant Activity of *Momordica dioica*

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ABSTRACT

Momordica dioica is a perennial, dioecious, cucurbitaceous family commonly known as kakrol, spiny gourd. It is used not only as preventive and curative agent for various diseases, as well as healing of health conditions like diabetes, inflammation, liver disorder, gastrointestinal conditions and reproductive problems. *Momordica dioica* is considered as an underutilized vegetable, although having significant presence of certain compounds containing higher nutritional value than many frequently consumed vegetables. The Methanolic and aqueous extract of fruits of *Momordica dioica* was investigated for its Phytochemical properties and analysis for its active chemical ingredients. Phytochemical analysis indicated that there was presence of phenolic compounds, triterpenoids, alkaloids, glycosides in aqueous as well as methanolic extracts. The antioxidant activity of this extract was evaluated by hydrogen peroxide scavenging assay. The result indicated that methanolic extract have more antioxidant activity (86.29%) than aqueous extracts (82.9%). In the modality of incorporating both traditional use and modern scientific validation of plant-based therapeutics to build an environment of safe, effective, and cost-effective drug development.

Keywords: *Momordica dioica*, fruit extract, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, antioxidant activities

INTRODUCTION

Momordica dioica is a perennial, dioecious, cucurbitaceous climbing creeper. Common name of it is spine gourd, teasel gourd or small bitter gourd worldwide whereas in Bangladesh it is called as kakrol and in India as kankro, kartoli, kantoli, kantola, kantoli, ban karola, or janglee karela. Kakrol is about 5–7 meters in length, a popular seasonable vegetable of which its fruit, young twigs and leaves are used as vegetable. It is used not only as preventive and curative agent for various diseases but also as vegetable with a significant nutritional value over thousands of years (Talukdar & Hossain, 2014). *Momordica dioica* belongs to the family Cucurbitaceae and under the genus *Momordica*, a genus of annual or perennial climbers that contains about 80 species (Venkateshwarlu, 2017). The fruits of *Momordica dioica* shows various medicinal properties like analgesics, anti-tumorogenic, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic activity and anti-cancer activity [Sastri *et al.* 1962]. The size of fruit is 2 to 3 cm in diameter. Weight of this fruit is

2.9 to 5 gm. Flowering typically occurs from June to July, with the fruiting period extending from September to November. It is native to Asia with extensive distribution in India and Bangladesh. The green fruits, young twigs and leaves of this crop are used as vegetable or cooked as a vegetable. (Jadhav & Kamble, 2022). Leaves 1.5-4 inches long, cordate, acute more or less 3-5 lobed; Flowers large, dioecious and yellow in colour; Fruit 1-3 inches long, shortly beaked, densely covered with soft spines (Rasul *et al.* 2004). This is climbing creeper generally found throughout India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Himalayas to Ceylon. Reported up to an altitude of 1500 m in Assam and Garo hills of Meghalaya (Ram *et al.* 2002). Kakrol is a Cucurbitaceous crop originated in the Indo - Malayan region (Kirtikar *et al.* 1999). Fruits are the juicy seeds-bearing structures of blooming plants that can be eaten. In respiratory conditions, the extract of the leaves or fruit is applied in the ailments such as asthma, bronchitis and chronic cough. The fruit powder is applied for skin disorders (Asha *et al.*, 2025). Antioxidants are groups of compounds that neutralize free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the cell. Polyphenols, flavonoids, carotenoids are the phytochemicals which are rich in antioxidant properties (Bhende *et al.* 2025). The edible fruit of *M. dioica* was found to have an average nutritional value of 84.1% moisture, 7.7% carbohydrates, 3.1% protein, 3.1% fat, 3.0% fibre, and 1.1% minerals (Asha *et al.*, 2025). The fruit also contain alkaloid, flavonoids, glycosides and amino acids (Kushwaha *et al.* 2016). The fruit contains a high amount of vitamin C The fruit is rich in ascorbic acid and contain iodine (Rao, 2001). The fruit also contain alkaloid, flavonoids, glycosides and amino acids (Kushwaha *et al.*, 2005) *Momordica dioica* also contains an alkaloid, a fragrant extractive matter and ash 3 to 4 p.c. Ash contains a trace of manganese. The Methanolic and aqueous extract of fruits of *Momordica dioica* was investigated for its Phytochemical properties and analysis for its active chemical ingredients.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collection and preparation of plant material:

100gm of *M. dioica* fruits were collected from local market, Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar. Fruits were sliced into small pieces and dried at room temperature in shade and a fine powder was prepared through a grinder. Suitable plant extracts were prepared for preliminary phytochemical evaluation and assessment

activity. The study on *M. dioica* was carried out during the period between June, 2025 to December, 2025.

Preparation of Extract:

Fruit extract was prepared by four extraction methods v.z Hot extract, Aqueous extract, successive solvent extraction (methanol followed by aqueous).

Hot extract: 10 gm of fruit extract was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water and boiled extract for 10 to 15 minutes, then cooled at room temperature and filtrate,

Aqueous extract: 10 gm of fruit extract was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water and placed extract into shaker incubator for 3 to 4 days. The sample was filtrate.

Methanolic extract: 10 gm of fruit extract was dissolved in 100 ml of pure methanol and placed it into shaker incubator for 3 to 4 days. The filtrate same was used (R.G. Kasute.*et al.* 2025).

Methanol Aqueous extract: Methanol extracted residue (9.34g) was collected and dried, then added it in 100 ml distilled water. Then placed the extract into shaker incubator for 3 to 4 days. filtrate the sample for further analysis.(Jadhav SR. *et al.* 2022).

Fig. 1: A: Fresh fruits of *Momordica dioica*
B. Shade Dried fruits of *Momordica dioica*

Phytochemical analysis:

1) Test for carbohydrates: Molish test:

1ml extract was treated with two drops of alcoholic α - naphthol solution in tube and then 0.5 ml. Concentrated sulphuric acid were added carefully

along the sides of test tubes. Formation of violet ring between two liquids. (Silva *et al.* 2017, Zeonu CSs. *et al.* 2016).

2) Test for reducing sugars: Fehling's test:

1ml extract, 0.5ml fehling's solution A and 0.5ml fehling's solution B were added in test tube and heated on water both for 10 min, formation of red precipitate (Zeonu C.S..*et al.*2016).

3) Test for proteins: Biuret test:

Equal volume of Biuret reagent to 1ml sample was added, mixed, and waited for 3-5 minutes for the colour change. Formation of the violet or purple color. (Sheel R.*et al.*201).

4) Test for alkaloids: Mayer's test:

1ml extract was taken in test tube and few drops of Mayer's reagent was added into it and then cream color precipitate was observed.

5) Test for flavonoids: Alkaline reagent test:

1ml extract was treated with few drops of NaOH solution separately in test tube formation of intense yellow color which become Colorless on addition of few drops of diluted acid indicates presence of flavonoids.

6) Test for triterpenoids: Salkowski's test:

1 ml of sample was taken,3 to 4 drops of concentrated.H₂SO₄ was added, then it was shaken well and allowed to stand for 2 minutes. Formation of golden yellow layer at the bottom.

7) Test for diterpenes: Copper acetate test:

1ml of plant extract was taken to test tube and 3-4 drops of copper acetate solution was added. Formation of emerald green colour.

8) Test for carboxylic acid: Effervescence test:

1 ml of sample was taken in a test tube and then 1 ml of sodium bicarbonate solution was added, formation of effervescence. (Kocadas *et al.* 2017).

9) Test for cardiac glycosides: Keller-Killani test:

1 ml of sample was taken, then 1.5 ml of glacial acetic acid, then 1 drop of 5 % ferric chloride and concentrated H₂SO₄ was added. Formation of brown colour ring indicated the presence of cardiac glycosides (Deshpande *et al.* 2014).

10) Phenolic test:

1ml extract and few drops of iodine reagent. Transient red colour was observed.

Antioxidant activity: Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) scavenging assay

Antioxidant activity assay was performed for S. methanol and S. aqueous extract. A set of 9 test tubes were prepared, for control, test add 0.5 ml of H₂O₂,1 ml phosphate buffer, 0.4 ml distilled water was added in test and control, While in blank instead H₂O₂, 0.5 ml extra phosphate buffer was added, Then 1 ml of sample was added in test and 1ml ascorbic acid was added in control, then 2 ml of dichromic acetic acid was added after and interval of (15,30,45,60 seconds) respectively in all tubes, were kept for boil water bath for 10min, OD was taken at 240 nm..% of scavenging activity of H₂O₂ by fruit extract was calculated. 2 ml of dichromic acetic acid with interval of 15,30,45,60 seconds was added as mentioned. (Bhende *et al.* 2025, Kasute *et al.* 2025; Anant *et al.* 2019).

RESULTS

Phytochemical analysis: The extracted sample of *Momordica dioica* fruits revealed the presence of therapeutically important bioactive compounds like alkaloids, glycosides, triterpenoids, phenolic compounds, proteins, carbohydrates, diterpenes, carboxylic acid, cardiac glycosides (Table 1).

Antioxidant activity: Antioxidant assays play an essential role in optimal performance and cost-effective assessment of antioxidant capacities of natural products such as medicinal plants and food samples. (Anant *et al.* 2019, Kasute *et al.* 2025). Antioxidants are groups of compounds that neutralize free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the cell

$$\text{Scavenging activity\% (H}_2\text{O}_2) = \frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \times 100$$

Where A₀ is the absorbance of the control and A₁ is the absorbance in the presence of the extract and standard.

The Figure No. 3. the antioxidant activity of S. aqueous extract for 15 sec, 45 sec, 60 sec was high than the S. methenolic extract. S. Methenolic extract the antioxidant activity was more for 30 seconds. The S. methenolic and S. aqueous extract both having good antioxidant activity.

Table 1: Detection of phytochemicals in *Momordica dioica* fruits

Sr. No	Tests	Aqueous extract (A)	Boiling extract (B)	S. Aqueous extract (C)	S. Methanolic extract (D)
Detection of Carbohydrates					
1	Molish test	+	+	+	+
2	Fehling's test	+	+	+	+
Detection of Alkaloids					
3	Mayer's test	+	-	-	+
Detection of proteins					
4	Biuret test	+	+	+	+
Detection of flavonoids					
5	Alkaline test	-	+	-	+
Detection of Phenolic compounds					
6	Iodine test	+	-	+	-
Detection of triterpenoids					
7	Salkowski's test	+	+	+	+
Detection of diterpenes					
8	Copper acetate test	+	+	+	+
Detection of carboxylic acid					
9	Effervescence test	+	+	+	-
Detection of cardiac glycosides					
10	Keller-killani test	+	+	+	-

Figure 3. Antioxidant Activity assay

DISCUSSION

Bioactive compounds confirmed by various qualitative test. Bhende *et al.* (2025) has worked on phytochemical profiling and antioxidant activity of *Momordica dioica* fruits. The study has revealed the presence of alkaloids, steroids, triterpenoids, flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, triterpenes, and other bioactive compounds. The fruit is rich in nutrients,

containing high levels of carbohydrates, protein. In our present work also obtained the presence of carbohydrates, proteins and secondary metabolites such as Triterpenoids, Diterpenes, glycosides in four extracts. Alkaloids were present in aqueous and methanolic extract but absent boiling and S. aqueous extracts while phenolic compounds were present in aqueous and S. aqueous extract.

Bhende Kailas *et al.* in 2025 and Kasute *et al.* in 2025 worked on the antioxidant activity in *Momordica dioica* fruits and lichens exhibits significant antioxidant activities for crude extract 20.64%, Purified sample for glycosides 40.32% and alkaloids 24.06% respectively. Keser *et al.* in 2012 has revealed the plant *Crataegus monogyna* exhibits antioxidant activity for aqueous extract (15.44%). In the study the result indicated that S. methanolic extract have more antioxidant activity (86.29%) than S. aqueous extracts (82.9%). which may contribute to its potential in preventing and managing oxidative stress-related diseases

The successful extraction also indicated that the *Momordica dioica* sample used in the current study was more potent in extractable phytochemical constituents and Scavenging activity of S. methenolic extract was more than S. aqueous extract.

CONCLUSION

The result demonstrates the presence of phytochemicals of *Momordica dioica* fruit extract S. methanolic and S. aqueous extract contained alkaloids, phenolic, diterpenes, triterpenes, flavonoids and cardiac glycosides. S. methanolic and S. aqueous extract found to be with significant antioxidant activity.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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